

Problems of Women Workers in Unorganised Sector: with Special Reference to Prakasam District of Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract:- Women workers in India have always been active contributors to the national income. Their contributions, however, have rarely been acknowledged, thus far. An important characteristic of the Indian female workforce is that most of it is employed in the unorganised or the informal sector, currently estimated to be 78.4 per cent of the total women workers. The percentage goes up to 80.7 per cent, if women working in the urban areas are also included. Women are not recognised as workers and even though they put in long hours of work and the returns are very low. They have limited access to tools and equipment, innovations in communications and technology almost completely bypass them. They face multiple entry barriers into the main stream markets; use of social protection is restricted. According to these dimensions, the present paper highlighted that the problems of women workers in various activities in unorganised sector of select Prakasam district.

Keywords:- Women Workers, Low Wage, Poverty, Training, and Irregular Payment.

I. INTRODUCTION

The country like India is known as its great geographical spread diversity and enormity of its population. India has a population of more than a billion as per the last census survey in which women constitute nearly half of the population and play a vital role in rural and urban economies. Present, scenario, the economic position is shown comparatively lower than males. As far as social status is concerned they have more responsibilities and duties in society. The paradoxical situation arises as such a when somewhere women are praised as a goddess and sometimes treated as a slave. Women had to countenance many difficulties during post Vedic and heroic ages. Women in India are always reliant on male members of relations; they are not allowed to speak in front of elders or in-laws. She was always been made responsible for every mistake. Now, from the early twentieth century, their status has been improved a little. After the independence of India constitutional makes and national leaders strongly abolished some act and initiated new act for equal social status. As a result, today's position of women has occupied in every field with a respectable position. Yet, they

have not absolutely free from some discrimination and harassment of society.

In India, the informal sector is commonly referred to as the 'unorganised sector' and the workers working there are referred to as 'unorganized workers'. The term 'informal economy' is used conjointly to represent the informal/unorganised sector and informal/unorganised workers. Unorganised sector workers are characterised by low educational level, poor financial capacity, possessing at best low-end skills, inferior working condition, and low bargaining capacity due to lack of the organisational skills. Workers in the unorganised sector get low wages and if they are self-employed, their income is usually very low.

National commission on Labour (1966-69) has defined unorganized labour as those who have not been able to organize themselves in pursuit of common objectives on account of constraints like casual nature of employment, ignorance and illiteracy, small and scattered size of establishments and position of power enjoyed by employers because of the nature of industry.

It is well known that the women all over the world are part and parcel of the labour market. But it is also true those women everywhere are excluded from crucial economic activities. For example, in the agriculture sector in India, women are employed in production, processing and preservation of agriculture products, but are not much active in plugging. In both rural and urban areas they are engaged in work which sometimes has either no exchange value or very low exchange value. The inferior status and poor facilities offered to them vis a vis. Males accentuates further their poor economic conditions and pushes them into the unorganised sector. Some times because of restrictions put against them they are enable to enter into unorganised sector. In unorganised sector they are employed as domestic servants, sweepers, construction workers, brick line workers, agro industries workers and self employed workers in knitting, sewing and weaving etc. Due to certain economic compulsions these women are pushed to low productivity jobs.

The time women's spend on paid and unpaid work is typically greater than the time men's spend in the labour market. Unpaid family work is rarely recorded in official

statistics. It manifests itself only indirectly in the labour market in the form of gender differences in labour force participation rates, sector of employment, hours of work, and wage level.

On the whole, labour force participation rates for women are lower than those for men. However, these differences are often exaggerated because the definition of the participation rate fails to capture many aspects of women’s work, particularly time spent on child bearing and other household tasks. Men are usually in the labour force throughout the prime working years (age 20-60), and their participation rates are typically more than 90 per cent in virtually every country. Female participation rates vary widely across countries. In 1990, for every 10 men in the labour force there were two women in the Middle East and North Africa, three in south Asia, 6 in sub Saharan Africa, and seven in south East Asia (United Nations 1991). Worldwide, 41 per cent of women are age of 15 years or more are in the labour force, but in developing countries is 31 per cent. These numbers are deceptive, however, because they don’t take into account, the agriculture work that women do in developing countries of the world.

➤ Objectives

- To study the theoretical background of unorganised sector
- To analyse the problems of women workers in unorganised sector in Prakasam district of Andhra Pradesh
- To draw the conclusions

II. METHODOLOGY

➤ Sample Design

The present study covers only Prakasam district of Coastal Andhra of Andhra Pradesh. The district is one of the drought prone-area in Coastal Andhra in Andhra Pradesh. The district classified in three revenue division like Ongole, Kanigiri and Markapuram. Each revenue division four mandal were selected and each mandal 30 women workers were selected. Altogether, three revenue divisions, twelve mandals and 360 sample women worker respondents in prakasam district.

➤ Data Collection

The present study is based on both primary and secondary data. The researcher has gone through primary data with the help to pre-structure personal interview schedule for collecting information regarding socio-economic status and also their problems of women workers engaged in domestic workers in unorganised sector.

The secondary data were also collected from various sources like journals, books, published and unpublished theses, dailies, government reports, and various university libraries.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Low Wages

In Indian society, majority of the organisations are called MSME’s and also rural area organisations are unorganised industries. These unorganised sectors did not follow the rules and regulations. In this directions minimum wage act also should not implement strictly. According to this the researcher has found that the opinion of the sample respondents in case of receiving low wages through five point scale.

Table: 1 Opinion of the women workers on low wages

S. No	Opinion	Frequency	%	Weighted average
1	Strongly agree	234	65.00	0.92
2	Agree	76	21.00	
3	Can’t say	18	05.00	
4	Disagree	14	04.00	
5	Strongly disagree	18	05.00	
	Total	360	100.00	

Source: Field Survey

The present table discussed that the opinion of the sample women workers have been receiving low wages and collected opinion on this dimensions, analyzed and presented in table 1.

The table demonstrated that the opinion of the respondents was classified into five point scale like strongly agree, just agree, can’t say, disagree, and strongly disagreed. Among these, 65 per cent of the women workers have strongly agreed on getting low wages from the employer, 21 percent were just agreed, 4 per cent of them stated disagreed, and 5 per cent of the respondents strongly disagreed.

Fig 1 Opinion on low wages

It is clearly concluded from the above table that generally the women workers have been getting lower wages because most of the women labourer have don't much aware about minimum wage system/Act in Indian society. So, the unorganised sector women have been less wages in the study area.

B. Lack of training

Training programme is process of acquiring knowledge, enhancing skills for reaching organisational objectives/goals. Every organisation has been conducting various training programmes at various levels. In this context, the women workers have entered into organisation without any knowledge, skills, experience so that they performed and contributed very less in initial period. According to them, the researcher has concentrated on women problems like lack of training at unorganised sector to women.

Table: 2 Respondent responses on lack of training in unorganised sector

S. No	Opinion	Frequency	%	Weighted average
1	Strongly agree	256	71.00	0.79
2	Agree	22	06.00	
3	Can't say	42	12.00	
4	Disagree	29	08.00	
5	Strongly disagree	11	03.00	
Total		360	100	

Source: Field Survey

The above table shows that the opinion of the women workers and their opinion on training programme in Prakasam district. It is depicted that two third of the selected sample workers have stated that lack of training programme they should not get required skills and knowledge, 12 per cent of them have neutral and 11 per cent of the respondents do not required any training programme in their working organisation.

Fig 2 Opinion on lack of training

It is finally concluded that who are working in garments, beauty parlal, etc those women have required additional skills otherwise rest of the women need not to any training programme such as agricultural labour and domestic works.

C. Poverty

In Indian society, A large size of the women workers have been living under the below poverty line in both urban and rural areas. Uneducated women did not much more knowledge and awareness among various economic activities in this society. So, that numbers of families have depended on one income members. Hence, there is no fulfilling their numbers needs and wants properly. According to this, the women will also take responsible and started to earning some times and added to total income family income.

Table: 3 Opinion of women workers on poverty

S. No	Opinion	Frequency	%	Weighted average
1	Strongly agree	223	62.00	0.79
2	Agree	65	18.00	
3	Can't say	22	06.00	
4	Disagree	43	12.00	
5	Strongly disagree	07	02.00	
Total		360	100	

Source: Field Survey

In this context, the researcher has noticed various problems of the women and poverty is one of the major problem facing by the female workers in Prakasam district,

The present table potroyat that the opinion of the selected women workers on their poverty. It can be discloses that 62 percent of the respondents have expressed that strongly agreed, 18 percent of the respondents are expressed just agreed, 14 per cent of them has given negative response and only 6 per cent were neutral.

It can be concluded that majority of the women respondents have stated that due to poverty, they have been enter into unorganised sector.

D. Irregular wage payment

The unorganised sector should not follow the rules and regulations, principles and various government and competent authority guidelines. So, nobody questioning to employer because of unemployment problem, number of employees were not treated as a human being of every worker in their organisation. And they paid low wages, less respect, high risk, high productivity, less quotation and irregular payment.

Table: 4 Opinion on irregular wage payment by the women

S. No	Opinion	Frequency	%
1	Strongly agree	162	45.00
2	Agree	140	39.00
3	Can't say	54	15.00
4	Disagree	04	01.00
5	Strongly disagree	00	00.00
	Total	360	100

Source: Field Survey

The women worker have addressed irregular payment is one of the problem in the study area. According to this context, the researcher has collected empirical data, tabulated, analysed and presented in table 4. It is found that nearly 84 percent of the women worker in unorganised sector opined that they have given positive response on social problems.

It is clearly concluded from the study that majority of the respondents were accepted to receiving wages irregularly from this employer.

E. Sexual Harassment

In organised and unorganised sector, the women workers are highly vulnerable to sexual exploitation by their employers. Due to poverty, illiteracy, low awareness on various Act, the women workers have unreported to any time on their boss. Still these situations have been occurring in every society and there is no right mechanism to overcome these problems in this sector.

Table: 5 Details of opinion of respondents on sexual harassment

S. No	Opinion	Frequency	%	Weighted average
1	Strongly agree	112	31.00	-0.17
2	Agree	21	06.00	
3	Can't say	43	12.00	
4	Disagree	148	41.00	
5	Strongly disagree	36	10.00	
	Total	360	100	

Source: Field Survey

The present table reveals and found that 37 per cent of the sample women workers have positively responded and agreed stated statement, and 12 per cent of the respondents did not stated any opinion on this statement. It is further found more than 50 per cent of the respondents' opinion ranges from disagreed to strongly agree.

It is clearly concluded from the empirical study, less sample respondents have been suffering from their boss/employer and majority of them did not face such kind of problems in the study.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In Indian unorganised sector, women have been facing number of problems at work place due to low education, low awareness, less support, and fear. Hence, the government and NGOs have been taken up various awareness programmes and governmental safeguards to reduce the problems of women workers in unorganised sector. It is implemented Article 43 of the Indian constitutions states that the states shall endeavour to secure by suitable legislation or economic organisation or in any other way to all workers, agricultural, industrial, or otherwise, a living wage, conditions of work ensuring a decent standard of life and full enjoyment of leisure and social and cultural opportunities and it ensures equality for women.

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